

Supplementary Figure 1. Human dermal fibroblasts derived from patient with *Osteogenesis imperfecta* show morphological changes during reprogramming.

Pictures of reprogrammed somatic cells demonstrate changes of cells morphology within the time. Small clots has been observed since day 13. Treated cells form colonies at a day 17. The well-formed iPSC colonies are indicated with arrows (day 19). The scale bars in panel represent 200 μm . The images are representative of the analysis of at least 10 views and 3 independent experiments.

Supplementary Figure 2. STAR and its polyplex do not show the cytotoxicity for induced Pluripotent Stem cells.

STAR cytotoxicity was assessed before the use in homologous recombination in order to repair mutation in *COL1A1* gene. Polyethylenimine (PEI) was used as control and shows high cytotoxicity. The cells viability after treatment with polymer STAR reaches a value of 87% for STAR and 82% at the highest N/P for its polyplex with pDNA and correct linear DNA fragment. These results are representative of at least 3 independent experiments.

Supplementary Table 1. Primers used for amplification of the DNA fragment including mutation site.

Forward primer (5'-3')	Reverse primer (5'-3')
GCAACACTCCATGACCACAG	ACTGCAATCTTCACGGGAGC